

Synthesis and Selected Reactions of 9-(2-Cyanoethyl)-1-oxa-9-azatricyclo[4.2.1.0^{2,8}]nonan-3-one-6-carbonitrile

S A EL-ABBADY* and S M AGAMAI

Department of Chemistry, University College for Girls, Ain Shams University, Heliopolis, Cairo, Egypt

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Oxirination of the activated 3,4-olefinic double bond of 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-en-2-one-6-carbonitrile (1) with basic hydrogen peroxide afforded 9-(2-cyanoethyl)-1-oxa-9-azatricyclo[4.2.1.0^{2,8}]nonan-3-one-6-carbonitrile (2). Ring opening of the oxirane ring in 2 has been investigated using 10% sodium hydroxide, acetic acid and phenylhydrazine to give 4, 7 and 8 respectively.

The reaction of 3-pyridinol with acrylonitrile and methyl acrylate constitute simple one-pot high yield conversions into complex tropane-like alkaloid, 8-substituted-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octenone derivatives¹. 1,3-Diplo cycloaddition reactions are reversible thermally, photochemically and electron impact^{1,2}. Compounds of the type 1 undergo ready retro-1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions under thermal conditions to yield 3-pyridinol¹. The reversibility of such reactions and the availability of the substrate (1) in high yield make those type of compounds as valuable synthetic intermediates. In previous work, we have attempted to exploit such retroreactions for the synthesis of 4- and 5-methyl-3-pyridinols². However, all attempts to get the key intermediate 2,3-dicarbonyl cycloadduct either by selenium dioxide oxidation or with isoamyl nitrite with the hydrogenated cycloadduct¹ had failed with the view to prepare 3,4-dihydropyridine. Now, we wish to report herein the oxirination of the activated 3,4-olefinic double bond of 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-en-2-one-6-carbonitrile (1) to give 9-(2-cyanoethyl)-1-oxa-9-azatricyclo[4.2.1.0^{2,8}]nonan-3-one-5-carbonitrile (2), which is considered to be a convenient source of the key intermediate 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-3,4-dihydroxy-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octane-2-one-6-carbonitrile required for the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyridine.

α,β -Unsaturated ketones with peracids usually do not lead to oxirination of the double bond. The reaction with conjugated ethylenic double bond is retarded sufficiently so that the reaction of peracid with carbonyl group usually becomes the predominant process. However, oxirination of α,β -unsaturated ketones can be accomplished directly by nucleophilic reagents such as sodium salt of hydrogen peroxide. Thus, 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-en-2-one-6-carbonitrile, the substrate (1) has been oxirinated by hydrogen peroxide in 5% sodium hydroxide at room temperature. The oxirane (2) obtained was characterised by means of periodate test³ and spectral evidence. Its spectrum of 2 displayed stretching frequency characteristic of non-conjugated carbonyl group at 1720 and $\nu_{C=N}$ at 2225 cm^{-1} . The stretching frequencies characteristic of the olefinic C-H and the conjugated olefinic double bond were found to disappear. The λ_{max} at 224.5 nm which is charac-

teristic of the enone chromophors⁴ in 1 also disappeared in 2. The ¹H nmr spectrum of 2 displayed upfield shielded protons and lack the down-field 3,4-vinylic protons: 5.4 (H-4, d, $J_{4,2\text{-endo}}$ 2 Hz, $J_{4,5\text{-endo}}$ 5 Hz, $J_{4,5\text{-exo}}$ 10 Hz), 3.5 (H-2, dd, $J_{4,2\text{-endo}}$ 2 Hz, $J_{2\text{-endo-8-endo}}$ 8 Hz), 5.1 (H-8, dd, $J_{8,2}$ 8 Hz, $J_{8,7}$ 6 Hz), 5.8 (H-7, d, $J_{7,8\text{-endo}}$ 5 Hz, $J_{7,6\text{-endo}}$ is small enough to be neglected), 3.9 (H-6, m), 2.98 (H-5-*exo*-overlapped with the other signal), 2.1 (H-5-*endo* J, not measurable owing to signal overlap). The splitting pattern of H-2 and H-8 as double doublets is compatible with the *exo*-stereochemistry of the fused oxirane ring. The corresponding *endo*-oxirane derivative resulting from *endo*-face attack has not been detected. The substrate (1) separated as yellow viscous oil from a column of alumina has been proved to be an inseparable isomeric mixture of 6-*endo*- and 6-*exo*-carbonitrile stereoisomers in almost equal amounts, based on ¹H nmr evidence¹. However, the *exo*-configuration of the 6-carbonitrile group in 2 has been assigned from the splitting pattern of H-7 in ¹H nmr spectrum. H-7 appears as a doublet at 5.8 ppm due to negligible $J_{7,6\text{-endo}}$ coupling. The 6-*endo*-stereoisomer has not been detected. The isolation of the oxirane (2) has 6-*exo*-carbonitrile group which indicates that epimerisation at carbon-6 has taken place under the influence of sodium hydroxide in the reaction mixture. This is not surprising, since H-6 is acidic enough due to the adjacent electron-withdrawing carbonitrile group. Abstraction of the 6-*endo*-proton by the hydroxide anion yielded the stabilised carbanion. Recombination with proton, gives the more thermodynamically stable 6-*exo*-carbonitrile stereoisomer (2). The mass spectrum of the oxirane (2) displayed the expected molecular ion at m/z 217 a.m.u. A mechanism is suggested for the subsequent fragmentations of the molecular ion in the ionisation chamber (Scheme 1).

The isolation of the oxirane (2) in substantial amount lead us to investigate the ring opening of the strained oxirane ring by acetic acid and sodium hydroxide, with the view to get the key intermediate 3,4-glycol. Thus, treatment of ethanolic solution of 2 with 10% aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide at room temperature afforded a yellow solid identified as a tautomeric mixture of 3-hydroxy-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-en-2-one-6-*exo*-carbonitrile (4a) and 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octan-

Scheme 1 Fragmentation of compound 2

2,3-dione-6-*exo*-carbonitrile (**4b**) from satisfactory elemental analyses and spectral evidence. The solid exhibited a broad ir band at 3 500–2 600 cm^{-1} assignable for the enolic group adjacent to the carbonyl group in which intramolecular hydrogen bonding is possible. The bands at 1 735, 1 720 and 1 670 cm^{-1} are for diketone, and α,β -unsaturated ketone in **4**. The band at 1 640 cm^{-1} is for conjugated C=C. ^1H nmr was found at δ 4.98 (H-1, d, $J_{1,7\text{-exo}}$ 8 Hz, $J_{1,7\text{-endo}}$ negligible). The signal for H-3 was found to disappear. Other signals were found at δ 6.95 (H-4, (4a), 1H, d, $J_{4,5}$ 6 Hz), 4.78 (H-4, 2H, dd, $J_{4\text{-exo},5}$ 6 Hz, $J_{4\text{-exo},4\text{-endo}}$ 14 Hz and $J_{4\text{-endo},5}$ negligible), 5.88 (H-5, (4a), d, $J_{5,4}$ 6 Hz) and 5.45 (H-5, (4b), d, $J_{5,4\text{-exo}}$ 6 Hz, $J_{5,4\text{-endo}}$ negligible, $J_{5,6\text{-endo}}$ negligible), 3.95 (H-6-*endo*, dd, $J_{6\text{-endo},7\text{-endo}}$ 8 Hz, $J_{6\text{-endo},7\text{-exo}}$ 10 Hz), 2.85 (H-7-*exo*, m, $J_{7\text{-exo},1}$ 8 Hz, $J_{7\text{-exo},6\text{-endo}}$ 10 Hz, $J_{7\text{-exo},7\text{-endo}}$ negligible). It is suggested that **4** is probably formed via elimination of water molecule under the influence of sodium hydroxide. H-3 in the non-isolated intermediate glycol is acidic in which it facilitates the base induced E-2 elimination process leading to **4a** together with its diketone-tautomer **4b**. Sublimation of the tautomeric mixture (**4a** and **4b**) under reduced pressure and in the presence of nitrogen atmosphere had failed due to the decomposition of the substance (Scheme 2). On the other hand, phenylhydrazine in acetic acid reacted with the tautomeric mixture (**4a** and **4b**) to give yellow needles (10%) m.p. 128–130°, identified as 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-3-hydroxy-4-phenylhydrazino-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octan-2-one-6-*exo*-carbonitrile (**8**). It exhibited a broad ir band at 3 650–2 850 (polymeric OH and NH), 2 225 (C \equiv N) and 1 740 cm^{-1} (non-conjugated C=O), 1 605, 1 540 and 1 550 (phenyl) and 750 cm^{-1} (C–H out-of-plane bending monosubstituted phenyl). It displayed ^1H nmr signals at δ 4.65 (H-1, dd, $J_{1,3}$ 2 Hz, $J_{1,7\text{-exo}}$ 10 Hz), 4.25 (H-3, dd, $J_{3,1}$ 2 Hz, $J_{3,4}$ 10 Hz), 4.88 (H-4, 3d, $J_{4,3}$ 10 Hz, $J_{4,5}$ 6 Hz, $J_{4,\text{NH}}$ 5 Hz), 5.35 (H-5, d, $J_{5,4}$ 6 Hz), 3.82 (H-6-*endo*, dd, $J_{6\text{-endo},7\text{-endo}}$ 8 Hz, $J_{7\text{-exo},7\text{-endo}}$ 10 Hz), 2.75 (H-7-*exo*, triple doublets, $J_{7\text{-exo},1}$ 8 Hz, $J_{7\text{-exo},6\text{-endo}}$ 8 Hz, $J_{7\text{-exo},7\text{-endo}}$ 14 Hz), 2.38 (H-7-*endo*, q, $J_{7\text{-endo},6\text{-endo}}$ 8 Hz, $J_{7\text{-endo},7\text{-exo}}$ 14

Scheme 2

Hz) The isolation of **8** indicated that (**4a**) constitutes the major component in the tautomeric mixture. Compound **4a** appears to be more thermodynamically stable than the diketone tautomer (**4b**) probably due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl group at position-3 with the adjacent carbonyl group.

Analogous treatment of the oxirane derivative (**2**) with glacial acetic acid gave the hydroxyacetate derivative, identified as 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-4-acetoxy-3-hydroxy-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octan-2-one-6-*exo*-carbonitrile (**7**) from elemental analysis and spectral evidence. It exhibited ir bands 3 480 (OH), 2 220 (C \equiv N), 1 725 (non-conjugated C=O) and 1 715 cm^{-1} (acetate C=O) and displayed ^1H nmr signals at δ 5.05 (H-1, dd, $J_{1,3}$ 6 Hz and $J_{1,7\text{-exo}}$ 10 Hz), 4.5 (H-3, dd, $J_{1,3}$ 6 Hz, $J_{3,4}$ 10 Hz), 4.85 (H-4, q, $J_{4,3}$ 10 Hz and $J_{4,5}$ 6 Hz), 5.55 (H-5, d, $J_{5,4}$ 6 Hz, $J_{5,6\text{-endo}}$ negligible), 3.9 (H-6-*endo*, dd, $J_{6\text{-endo},7\text{-exo}}$ 10 Hz, $J_{6\text{-endo},7\text{-endo}}$ 8 Hz), 2.24 (H-7-*endo*, dd, $J_{7\text{-endo},6\text{-endo}}$ 8 Hz, $J_{7\text{-endo},7\text{-exo}}$ 14 Hz, $J_{7\text{-endo},1}$ negligible). Further investigations concerning synthetic applications of the oxirane derivative (**2**) is currently under investigation.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 300 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference. All compounds were purified by column chromatography over alumina C-neutral (Fluka). Elemental analyses were performed at the University of Ain Shams, Cairo, Egypt.

9-(2-Cyanoethyl)-1-oxa-9-azatricyclo[4.2.1.0^{2,8}]nonan-2-one-6-*exo*-carbonitrile (2**):** To a solution of 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-en-2-one (**1**; 5 g, 0.025 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was added a homogeneous solution of 30% H_2O_2 (30 ml) followed by 5% aqueous NaOH (30 ml) dropwise while stirring. The stirring was continued for 1 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into water (~ 500 ml) and kept overnight at 0°. The separated oxirane derivative was crystallised from ethanol as creamy crystals (40%) m.p. 188–90°.

(Found : C, 61.08; H, 4.98; N, 19.11. $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_2$ requires : C, 60.82; H, 5.06; N, 19.35%).

Tautomeric mixture of 3-hydroxy-8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-en-2-one-6-exo-carbonitrile and 8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octane-2,3-dione-6-exo-carbonitrile (4b) : A mixture of oxirane (**2**; 1 g, 0.0046 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) and 10% aqueous NaOH (4 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water, neutralised with 10% HCl and extracted with ether. Ether layer was separated, washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ether was then evaporated on a steam-bath and the solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals, m.p. 160°d (Found : C, 60.39; H, 6.01; N, 21.23, $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_2$ requires : C, 60.82; H, 5.06; N, 19.35%).

8-(2-Cyanomethyl)-4-acetoxy-3-hydroxy-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octan-2-one-6-exo-carbonitrile (7) : A mixture of oxirane derivative (**2**; 1 g, 0.0046 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-cold water and neutralised with sodium bicarbonate solution. The organic material was extracted twice with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ether was driven off on a steam-bath. The colourless solid obtained was crystallised from

ethanol, (65%) m.p. 230°d (Found : C, 60.17; H, 5.85; N, 16.45. $C_{13}H_{15}N_3O_3$ requires : C, 59.77; H, 5.74; N, 16.09%).

8-(2-Cyanoethyl)-3-hydroxy-4-phenylhydrazino-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octan-2-one-6-carbonitril (8) : Tautomeric mixture (**4a** and **4b**; 1 g, 0.003 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) and phenylhydrazine (2 ml) in acetic acid (2 ml) were mixed and refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and left in a refrigerator overnight. The organic materials were then extracted with ether. The ether layer was separated and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of ether afforded a bright yellow oil and soon solidified as yellow needles (70%), m.p. 128–130° (Found : C, 62.95; H, 5.98, N, 21.11. $C_{19}H_{19}N_5O_5$ requires : C, 62.76; H, 5.84; N, 21.55%).

References

- 1 J BANERJI, N DENNIS, J FRANK, A R KATRITZKY and T MTSUO *J Chem Soc, Perkin Trans, I*, 1976, 2324
- 2 A H MOUSTAFA, S A EL ABBADY and S DONIA, *Bull Fac Sci, Ain Shams Univ (Egypt)*, 1983
- 3 H M WALTON *J Org Chem*, 1957, **22**, 1161, VIR VALENTE and J L WOLFHANGEN, *J Org Chem*, 1966, **31**, 2509, G B PAYNE and J H WILLIAMS, *J Org Chem*, 1959, **24**, 284, GORODETSKY, N DANIELI and Y MAZUR, *J Org Chem*, 1967, **32**, 760
- 4 A H EL ASKALANI, S A EI ABBADY, A A AL AHMADY, A M ABOU EL MAGD and A H MOUSTAFA, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1992, **69**, 306